

The Effect of Talent Management and Self-Efficacy through Motivation toward Performance of Population and Civil Notice of Simalungun District

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to analyze the effect of talent management and self-efficacy through motivation on performance of civil service and civil registry staff in Simalungun District. This type of research is quantitative descriptive. The population in this study were 74 people Simalungun district population and civil registry officials. The sampling method used is the census method where each member of the population is sampled. Primary data collection using questionnaires and secondary data collection using SEM or structural equation modeling with Smart PLS 3 analysis tools. The results of this study found that talent management has a positive and significant effect on performance. Self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on performance. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on performance. Self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on motivation. Then indirectly talent management through motivation has a positive and significant effect on performance and self-efficacy through motivation has a positive and significant effect on performance of the civil service and civil registry staff in Simalungun district.

Keywords: Talent Management, Self-Efficacy, Motivation, Employee Performance

INTRODUCTION

The development of current competencies is global, marked by a shift in economic conditions that has caused many companies to restructure. This is what drives changes in company management.

Human resources become one of the important elements in the changing economic conditions, because human resources themselves are the main foundation for companies that remain in the era of globalization. Human resources have the right control to determine the sustainability of a company. Competition of human resources in the current era of globalization is getting tighter, therefore human resources are expected to develop more effectively so as to achieve optimal business targets. In this situation the company must also know how to manage human resources in order to maintain the sustainability of the company in the economic balance. The main thing that companies need to pay attention to is regarding employee performance, because employee performance greatly influences the development and expected business results. To achieve optimal performance, companies must improve human resources because performance is directly proportional to human resources. While in the current global demands of economic change, there are still many human resources who have not been able to compete with the digital era that is currently being built, this is what makes the company in a dilemma situation in an effort to retain employees to achieve their business goals.

Effendi (2009) believes that performance is the result of work produced by employees or actual behavior that is determined according to their role in the

organization. Performance also means that achieved by someone both quality and quantity in accordance with the responsibilities given to him.

To produce quality human resources requires individuals who are always highly dedicated and professional who are able to make a meaningful contribution to the company. In carrying out the main tasks, responsibilities, authority in the field of its activities, human resources from superiors to lower level employees, need supporting factors.

Talent management according to Pella and Inayati (2011:81), talent management is a process of ensuring a company fills key positions of future leaders and positions that support the company's core competencies.

Self-efficacy is also able to encourage employees to show work suitability so that in the end they behave proactively because self-efficacy encourages a person to take a series of effective actions to change the environment. According to Alwisol (2004) self-efficacy is self-assessment, can do good or bad actions, right or wrong, can or cannot do as required. Lee and Bobko (1994) in Engko (2008), stated that individuals who have high self-efficacy will devote all their efforts and attention to achieving goals and failures that occur and make them try even harder.

Someone who has high self-efficacy is able to do something to change the events around him, while someone with low self-efficacy considers himself unable to do everything around him. In difficult situations, people who have low self-efficacy tend to give up easily, while people who have high self-efficacy will try even harder to overcome the challenges that exist. In other words, employees who feel important, strong, and enthusiastic about their work will show good performance.

Motivation is an important thing that must be a concern, because motivation is one of the factors that also determine a person's performance. Wibowo (2010) suggested that motivation is an impetus for

a series of processes of human behavior in achieving goals. Mangkunegara (2005) states motivation is formed from employee attitudes in dealing with work situations in the company. Motivation is a condition or energy that moves employees to be directed or directed to achieve the goals of the organization of the company. The mental attitude of employees who are pro and positive towards work situations is what strengthens their motivation to achieve maximum performance. Owned motivation is expected to be able to encourage oneself to be enthusiastic at work and will produce optimal performance. Talent management, self-efficacy, and motivation are factors that can affect performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Performance

The term performance comes from the word job performance or actual performance (work performance or actual achievement achieved by someone). Understanding employee performance is the work of quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out their duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him.

According to Mangkunegara (2007) employee performance is the result of quality and quantity of work achieved by an employee in carrying out their duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. Individual performance is the work of employees both in terms of quality and quantity based on predetermined work standards.

2.2 Motivation

According to Mathis and Jackson (2006) motivation is a desire in someone who causes the person to act. People act usually for a reason to achieve a goal. Hamzah (2011) divides motivation into two definitions, conceptually and operationally. The conceptual definition of work motivation is operationally, work motivation is defined as an internal and external drive for someone to do something

that is seen from the internal and external dimensions.

2.3 Self-Efficacy

Self-efficacy is one of the abilities of individual self-regulation. The concept of self-efficacy was first proposed by Bandura. Self-efficacy refers to perceptions about the ability of individuals to organize and implement actions to display certain skills (Bandura, 2006). Baron and Byrne (2000) suggest that self-efficacy is an individual's assessment of the ability or competence to carry out a task, achieve a goal, and produce something. In addition, Schultz and Schultz (1994) define self-efficacy as our feelings of adequacy, efficiency, and our ability to cope with life. Bandura (2006) explains that individual self-efficacy is based on four things, namely the experience of success, the experience of other individuals, verbal persuasion and physiological states.

2.4 Talent Management

The talent management theory states that the practical form of science and action. In the context of talent, where creativity must be the essence. This happens because many facts about the concept of talent are used in organizational management procedures. The concept of talent is very much applied by companies too. Talent cannot be measured and seen as being above average, but is measured in terms that match expectations.

RESEARCH METHODS

3.1 Types of Research

This type of research is causal research with a quantitative approach. According to Djarwanto (2004) the research aims to describe or describe the nature (characteristics) of a situation or object of research carried out through the collection and analysis of quantitative data and statistical testing.

The nature of this research is explanatory research. Sugiyono (2006) states that, explanatory research is research

that aims to explain the position of the variables studied as well as the relationship between one variable with another.

3.2 Research Place and Time

This research was conducted at the Population and Civil Registry Office of Simalungun Regency, in August 2019 to October 2019.

3.3 Population and Sample

Population is a generalization area that consists of a group of people, events or everything that has certain characteristics. Population is also a whole collection of elements related to what researchers expect in drawing conclusions (Ikhsan and Misri, 2012). The population in this study were all employees in the Population and Civil Registry Office of Simalungun Regency as many as 74 people.

According to Sugiyono (2006) the sample is a portion of the number and characteristics possessed by the population. In this study, the sampling method using the census method that is taking all 74 employees as samples.

3.4 Data Analysis Methods

According to Sugiyono (2006), data analysis is an activity after data from all respondents or other data sources has been collected. Activities in data analysis are grouping data based on variables and types of respondents, tabulating data based on variables from all respondents, presenting data for each variable studied, doing calculations to answer the problem formulation, and doing calculations to test the hypotheses that have been proposed. Data analysis was done using inferential statistical approaches.

RESULT

4.1 Direct Effect

The results of the SmartPLS algorithm in assessing Path Coefficient directly are given in Figure 1 and Table 1.

Source: PLS Output (2019)
Figure 1. Path Coefficient between Research Variables

Table 1. Path Coefficients

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Talent Management -> Kinerja Pegawai	0,241	0,240	0,122	1,970	0,049
Self Efficacy -> Kinerja Pegawai	0,271	0,277	0,153	1,775	0,077
Talent Management -> Motivasi	0,288	0,287	0,113	2,553	0,011
Self Efficacy -> Motivasi	0,575	0,580	0,084	6,812	0,000
Motivasi -> Kinerja Pegawai	0,371	0,362	0,114	3,267	0,001

Source: PLS Output (2019)

Following is the discussion of each hypothesis test based on the test results summarized in Table 1:

a)Effect of Talent Management on Performance

Based on Table 1 explains that the influence of talent management on performance ($p = 0.049 < 0.1$) then H_0 is rejected H_1 is accepted, meaning that there is a positive and significant influence between talent management and employees. Hypothesis H_1 , there is the influence of talent management on performance.

b)Effect of Self-Efficacy on Performance

Based on Table 1 explains that the effect of self-efficacy on performance ($p = 0.077 > 0.1$) then H_0 is rejected H_1 is accepted, meaning that there is a positive and significant effect between self-efficacy and

performance. The H_2 hypothesis, there is an effect of self-efficacy on performance.

c)Effect of Talent Management on Motivation

Based on Table 1 explains that the influence of talent management on motivation ($p = 0.011 < 0.1$) then H_0 is rejected H_1 is accepted, meaning that there is a positive and significant effect between talent management and motivation. Hypothesis H_3 , there is the influence of talent management on motivation.

d)Effect of Self-Efficacy on Motivation

Based on Table 1 explains that the effect of self-efficacy on motivation ($p = 0.000 < 0.1$) then H_0 is rejected H_1 is accepted, meaning that there is a positive and significant effect between self-efficacy and motivation. Hypothesis H_4 , there is an effect of self-efficacy on motivation.

e)Effect of Motivation on Performance

Based on Table 1 explains that the influence of motivation on performance ($p = 0.001 < 0.1$) then H_0 is rejected H_1 is accepted, meaning that there is a positive and significant influence between motivation and performance. Hypothesis H_5 , there is the influence of motivation on performance.

4.2 Indirect Effect

Indirect effect is the magnitude of influence through mediation variables. The magnitude

of the indirect effect is the multiplication between the direct effect of the independent variable on the mediating variable with the direct effect of the mediating variable on the

dependent variable, the magnitude of the indirect effect of the independent variable for variables can be calculated and summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Indirect Effect

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Talent Management -> Motivasi -> Kinerja Pegawai	0,107	0,110	0,058	1,855	0,064
Self Efficacy -> Motivasi -> Kinerja Pegawai	0,213	0,217	0,078	2,736	0,006

Source: PLS Output (2019)

Based on Table 2 above, the results of research to answer the hypotheses contained in the previous chapter are as follows:

a)Effect of Talent Management on Performance through Motivation

Table 2 shows that empirical evidence that talent management on performance through motivation, there is no indirect effect of talent management to performance through motivation with p values $0.064 < 0.1$. The bootstrap results indicate that this indirect effect is not significant; evaluating the contribution of the indirect effect to the total effect is 30.74%. H_0 accepted H_1 is rejected which means hypothesis 6 is rejected. But this is different if the p value requirement is 1.00, then there is a positive and significant influence between talent management on performance through motivation.

b)Effect of Self-Efficacy on Performance through Motivation

Self-efficacy can affect indirectly through motivation on performance with the fifth hypothesis being accepted. Self-efficacy towards performance through motivation, there is an indirect effect from self-efficacy to performance through motivation is 0.213. The bootstrap results indicate this indirect effect is significant, evaluating the contribution of indirect effect to the total effect is 44%, which is classified as partial mediation. Self-efficacy can affect indirectly through motivation on performance with the sixth hypothesis being accepted. After testing 74 respondents with the number of instrument questions as many as 38 item questions, it can be concluded that self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through motivation as an intervening variable.

The following is a table that shows the direct and indirect effects between research variables:

Table 3. Direct and Indirect Effect

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Talent Management -> Kinerja Pegawai	0,241	0,240	0,122	1,970	0,049
Self Efficacy -> Kinerja Pegawai	0,271	0,277	0,153	1,775	0,077
Talent Management -> Motivasi	0,288	0,287	0,113	2,553	0,011
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Self Efficacy -> Motivasi -> Kinerja Pegawai	0,213	0,217	0,078	2,736	0,006

Source: PLS Output (2019)

Based on Table 3 that talent management has a positive and significant effect on performance, self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on performance, then talent management and self-efficacy have a positive and significant effect on motivation, talent management has a positive and significant effect on performance through motivation, and self-efficacy has an effect positive and significant impact on performance through motivation.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis and discussion of the effect of talent management and self-efficacy through motivation on the performance of Simalungun District Civil Service and Civil Servants, a number of conclusions and suggestions can be drawn as follows:

- a) Talent management has a positive and significant effect on performance.
- b) Self-efficacy has a positive and not significant effect on performance.
- c) Talent management has a positive and significant effect on motivation.
- d) Self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on motivation.
- e) Motivation has a positive and significant effect on performance.
- f) Talent management has a positive and not significant effect on performance through work motivation.
- g) Self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on performance through work motivation.

SUGGESTION

Based on the above conclusions, which aim for the good and progress of the Population and Civil Registry Service Simalungun District, as follows:

- a) From the results of the study indicate that to improve the capability of talent management, it is necessary to emphasize the strategy of human resources starting from the system of recruitment, development, motivation to employees and efforts to retain employees who have

reliable talent. This is to ensure how the sustainability of government agencies as community servants is able to maintain better performance, and be able to use human resources as optimal as possible to improve performance in this technological age. And to improve self-efficacy there are several dimensions that must be evaluated, namely magnitude, generality and strength. This result must also be intervened by the leadership so that the self-efficacy of each employee can be seen so motivation is needed from the leadership, Intansi and coworkers to provide encouragement so that they take actions that show confidence in their abilities.

- b) It would be better for INSANSI to disseminate information about what is done by the agency so that each employee has high self-confidence, and has motivation so that the confidence can change into an action that leads positively, namely to improve performance.

Agencies should conduct training related to the routine tasks of each employee in order to be able to encourage the confidence of each employee, to keep employees more knowledgeable in new work completion so that they have more courage to make decisions by not delaying doing work on time and goals, and has the initiative to help get the job done better. Honesty, discipline, creativity, self-confidence and responsibility are the attitudes and actions of an employee who strongly supports work performance in a company. To get employees like this requires management talent that is truly pure so that the new employees are really accepted employees according to the needs of the agency. Placement of employees in accordance with care so that employees are more enthusiastic when doing work, do not feel burdened with the work provided so that employees do not feel full of work, because they feel the job is very compatible with his expertise.

- c) Provide material and non-material motivation on a regular basis, give employees incentives that are in accordance with performance, do not make a difference

between employee incentives and employee incentives from the same agency even though different districts / cities, because this will make employees lazy in completing work , or even choose not to be present.

d)For further researchers, it is important to expand the research so that more complete information will be obtained about what factors can affect the Performance of Employees in the Population and Civil Registry Office of Simalungun District. So that action can be taken to improve the factors that cause the low performance and can take appropriate steps to overcome the causes of the low performance. So that the Population and Civil Registry Office of Simalungun District can improve even better through the results of research conducted each study.

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